

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 99

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 99

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 99:1 ^aThe LORD reigns, let the peoples tremble; He ^{1b}is enthroned <i>above</i> the cherubim, let the earth shake! ² The LORD ¹is ^agreat in Zion, And He is ^bexalted above all the peoples. ³ Let them praise Your ^agreat and awesome name; ^bHoly is ¹He. ⁴ The ¹strength of the King ^aloves ²justice; You have established ^{3b}equity; You have ^cexecuted ²justice and righteousness in Jacob. ⁵ ^{1a}Exalt the LORD our God And ^bworship at His footstool; ^cHoly is He.</p> <p>Psa. 99:6 ^aMoses and Aaron were among His ^bpriests, And ^aSamuel was among those who ^ccalled on His name; They ^dcalled upon the LORD and He answered them. ⁷ He ^aspoke to them in the pillar of cloud; They ^bkept His testimonies And the statute that He gave them. ⁸ O LORD our God, You ^aanswered them; You were a ^bforgiving God to them, And <i>yet</i> an ^cavenger of their <i>evil</i> deeds.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 99:1</p> <p>יְהוָה מֶלֶךְ יִרְגָזוּ עַמִּים יָשֹׁב כְּרוּבִים תְּנוּט הָאָרֶץ : ² יְהוָה בְּצִיּוֹן גָּדוֹל וְרַם הוּא עַל-כָּל- הָעַמִּים : ³ יוֹדוּ שִׁמְדָּ גָדוֹל וְנוֹרָא קָדוֹשׁ הוּא : ⁴ וְעוֹ מֶלֶךְ מִשְׁפָּט אֲהַב אֶתָּה כּוֹנֵנֵת מִיִּשְׂרָאֵל מִשְׁפָּט וְצִדִּיקָה בִּיַעֲקֹב אֶתָּה עֹשֵׂת : ⁵ רוֹמְמוֹ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ וְהִשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְהַדָּם רַגְלָיו קָדוֹשׁ הוּא : ⁶ מֹשֶׁה וְאַהֲרֹן אֲבֹתֵינוּ וְשִׁמּוֹאֵל בְּקִרְיָת שָׁמוֹ קָרְאִים אֶל-יְהוָה וְהוּא יַעֲנֵם : ⁷ בְּעַמּוּד עָנָן יִדְבֵר אֲלֵיהֶם שִׁמְרוּ עֲדוֹתָיו וְחֻקֵּי נְתִן-לָמוֹ : ⁸ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ אֶתָּה עֲנִיתָם אֵל נִשְׂא תִיִּתָּ לָהֶם וְנִזְקָם עַל-עֲלִילוֹתָם : ⁹ רוֹמְמוֹ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ וְהִשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְתֵר קָדְשׁוֹ כִּי-קָדוֹשׁ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ :</p>

<p>⁹ Exalt the LORD our God And worship at His holy hill, For holy is the LORD our God.</p>	
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References

Psalm 99:1

¹Lit *sits*

^aPs 97:1

^bEx 25:22; 1 Sam 4:4; Ps 80:1

Psalm 99:2

¹Or *in Zion is great*

^aPs 48:1; Is 12:6

^bPs 97:9; 113:4

Psalm 99:3

¹Or *it*

^aDeut 28:58; Ps 76:1

^bLev 19:2; Josh 24:19; 1 Sam 2:2; Ps 22:3; Is 6:3

Psalm 99:4

¹Or *You have established in equity the strength of the King who loves justice*

²Or *judgment*

³Or *uprightness*

^aPs 11:7; 33:5

^bPs 17:2; 98:9

^cPs 103:6; 146:7; Jer 23:5

Psalm 99:5

¹The verb is plural

^aPs 34:3; 107:32; 118:28

^bPs 132:7

^cPs 99:3

Psalm 99:6

^aJer 15:1

^bEx 24:6-8; 29:26; 40:23-27; Lev 8:1-30

^c1 Sam 7:9; 12:18; Ps 22:4, 5

^dEx 15:25; 32:30-34

Psalm 99:7

^aEx 33:9; Num 12:5

^bPs 105:28

Psalm 99:8

^aPs 106:44

^bNum 14:20; Ps 78:38

^cEx 32:28; Num 20:12; Ps 95:11; 107:12

Targum

Psa. 99:1 The LORD reigns, the peoples will tremble; he whose presence abides among the cherubim will shake the earth. ² The LORD is great in Zion; and he is high over all the Gentiles. ³ They will confess his name, great and fearful; he is holy. ⁴ And you love the strength of the king of justice; you have established integrity; you have made justice and righteousness in Jacob. ⁵ Sing praise in the presence of the LORD our God, and bow down towards his sanctuary; he is holy. ⁶ Moses and Aaron are among his priests who gave their life for the people of the LORD, and Samuel prayed for them before the LORD, like the fathers of old, who prayed in his name; they would pray in his presence and he would answer them. ⁷ In the pillar of glorious clouds he would speak with them; they kept the commandments [of] his testimony, and the covenant that he gave to them. ⁸ O LORD our God, you answered them; you were a forgiving God for your people for their sake, and take vengeance for their deeds. ⁹ Sing praise in the presence of the LORD our God, and bow down towards the mount of his sanctuary, for the LORD our God is holy.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was composed by Moses and dedicated to the tribe of Dan. Dan was a strong tribe, and Moses said that Dan would have the opportunity to conquer the nations that were not obeying the LORD's Law. When the day of judgment comes, there will be a war against Gog and Magog. Israel will win the war, and the LORD's universal power will become unchallenged. Where are Gog and Magog located? Errico Rocco (Aramaic scholar) believes that Gog and Magog refer to Mongolia and China.

Notes about the Psalm

When the Messianic period commences, the Messiah will come to earth. The Zohar (the mystic writings) speaks about two Messiahs, Messiah ben Joseph and Messiah ben David. This idea arises from Zechariah 9:9, which says that the Messiah will be found riding a donkey and colt. The spiritual awareness is that the first Messiah, Messiah ben Joseph, will come to Israel to restore its spirituality. The nation will return to pure worship that is acceptable to the LORD. This first Messiah will return the secret Torah Moses received on Mount Sinai but was lost over the centuries. The spirituality of Israel must be restored before judgment day.

The second Messiah, Messiah ben David, will come afterward. This Messiah will restore the Kingdom of Israel and destroy any nation, not in allegiance with the LORD. The war of Gog and Magog will occur at that time. Therefore, the second Messiah is the warrior Messiah that the Israelites were waiting for when the Romans controlled the land of Judea.

An important note is that nothing in the Zohar indicates that the two Messiahs could not be the same person. Christianity moved toward this idea because the idea of the Messiah coming twice to earth is found in the Mithras cult. Mithras came to raise the spirituality of his followers. Those who followed Mithras were offered salvation through Mithras' death. When Paul converted the Mithras House Churches into Jesus House Churches, the theological doctrine of the Messiah coming twice to earth was retained.

For Jewish people, Jesus is not seen as the Messiah because they thought the Messiah ben David, would come first. This Messiah is the warrior they cried out for. The Christian view of Jesus being the Suffering Servant of Isaiah, chapters 50 to 55, was added to their doctrine because it fit into Jesus' life. These chapters would fit into the life of any prophet from the LORD. The sages said that these Isaiah chapters describe the nation of Israel as the suffering servant. Israel has worshiped and followed the LORD's ways for centuries and has always been under the oppression of foreign nations. Even when David and Solomon reigned, they still had to deal with invasions from surrounding nations.

Anyone who stands up for the LORD and tries to do His Will can find their life turning into the Suffering Servant of Isaiah 50-55. There are many forms of suffering that a person may have to endure if the person wants to fully serve the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

